

Conditional Quantum Probability $P(p/x)$ and Entropic Dynamics

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In previous notes, we suggested that quantum bound states may be analysed in terms of the conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ (where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction) which allows for the calculation of average kinetic energy at each point x i.e. $[\sum \text{over } p \text{ } p^2/2m P(p/x)]/W(x)$. This added to $V(x)$ yields E (average energy) at each x and yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation). We argued that probability is handled at the level of $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Measurements (even internal) may knock a particle from one p_1 state to another so another set of probabilities ($P(x)$ and $P(p)$) arise, $P(x)$ being based on: $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x)$. Averages of $f(p,x)$ follow from $P(x) \int f(p,x) P(p/x)$. Thus, there are two sets of probabilities in quantum mechanics.

Entropic dynamics (1) appears to begin with the probability $P(x)$ and considers a transition probability $P(x_1 | x)$ with $x_1 - x = \delta x$ an infinitesimal quantity. A product of transition probabilities is then taken to allow for finite $x_1 - x$ differences. It is stated in (1) that there exists information about x but not p . The maximization of entropy density may be used to determine the form of $P(x_1 | x)$. A "drift velocity" is also included (which is later shown to be related to the phase of the wavefunction). Ultimately, the Schrodinger equation is also obtained.

We argue one may use $P(p/x)$ to also calculate $P(x_1 | x)$ and compare this result with that obtained through the maximization of entropy density. A type of drift velocity appears naturally in this approach. We argue that the form $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ already incorporates statistical ideas (i.e. maximum entropy) in that the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ is identical for all x , endowing all x points with a "kind" of equivalent status. $\exp(ipx)$ is a function of p and x because one must calculate average kinetic energy at each x and this must change with x i.e. $K_{\text{ave}}(x) + V(x) = E$. Thus, we think there are strong similarities between entropic dynamics and the approach of using $P(p/x)$. There are also some differences in that the coefficient A of δx in $P(x_1 | x) = 1/Z \exp\{ A \delta x + B \frac{d\Phi}{dx} \delta x\}$ is treated as independent of x in entropic dynamics, but is a specific function of x (related to $d \ln(W)/dx$ or $d \ln(W)/dx + 1/W d^2W/dx^2$) in the $P(p/x)$ approach.

Approach of Entropic Dynamics

Following (1), entropic dynamics seems to be based on information about a particle's presence at x i.e. $P(x)$, but a lack of information regarding momentum. The focus is to calculate a transition probability $P(x_1 | x)$ for $x_1 - x = \delta x$ an infinitesimal quantity using the maximization of entropy and then multiply these transition probabilities to handle $x_1 - x$ being finite.

The entropy to be maximized is:

$$S = \int dx P(x_1 | x) \ln\{ P(x_1 | x) / Q(x_1 | x) \} \text{ where } Q(x_1 | x) \text{ is a prior. } \quad ((1))$$

The prior is obtained by maximizing:

$S_1 = \int dx_1 Q(x_1 | x) \ln\{ Q(x_1 | x) / M \}$ subject to N constraints: ((2))

$\delta(a,b) \delta(a,n) \delta(b,n) = k_n$ where k_n is a small number and $n=1$ to N

Here $\delta(a,b)$ is the Kronecker delta and $\delta(a,n) = x'(a) - x(a)$ which is taken to be a very small number. In other words, different small steps seem to be considered.

A Gaussian form is obtained for $Q(x_1 | x)$ after maximization of ((2)) (see (1)).

A second constraint is added to account for a drift potential ϕ whose average for small steps is:

$$\langle \delta \phi \rangle = \sum_{n=1}^N \delta(a,n) \frac{d\phi}{d\delta(a,n)} = k_1(x) \quad ((3))$$

Where $\delta(a,n)$ is again small.

In (1), gauge fields are also considered, such as the magnetic vector potential, but we ignore these in this note.

In (1), it is argued that the $P(x_1 | x)$ maximizing the entropy (1) is:

$$P(x_1 | x) = 1/Z \exp\{ - \sum_n \frac{a_n}{2} \delta(a,b) \delta x(a,n) \delta x(b,n) - a_1 \delta x(a,n) \left[\frac{d\phi}{dx} \right] \} \quad ((4))$$

where a_n and a_1 are constants (independent of x) and Z is the normalization constant. $\delta x(a,n)$ is a tiny value and the Sum on n suggests a product of many Gaussians, each representing a tiny $\delta x(a,n)$ step.

The objective of this note is to see if the approach using $P(p/x)$ yields an expression similar to ((4)).

Conditional Probability $P(p/x)$ Approach

We argue one may consider a momentum distribution $P(p/x)$ at each x . Thus, there is information about both p and x at each point, namely $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. We further argue that the form $\exp(ipx)$ is already statistical i.e related to maximum entropy because its modulus is 1 for all x points as for a free quantum particle. In other words, there is a certain equivalency of all x points as in a classical statistical gas. $\exp(ipx)$, however, is a function of x and p because, unlike a classical statistical gas, $\exp(ipx)$ is used to obtain an average $pp/2m$ (kinetic energy) at each x point which must vary with x according to $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$. Furthermore, by maximizing entropy, the form $\exp(ipx)$ also displays periodicity which appears experimentally throughout quantum mechanics. This periodicity is perhaps obscured in $P(x_1 | x)$, although later the Schrodinger equation is derived which also has this periodicity built in (e.g. consider the case of $V(x)=0$ but infinite at the walls).

The goal now becomes to find:

$$P(x_1) = P(x_1 | x) P(x) \quad ((5))$$

where $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$. We have noted in previous notes that there are two sets of probabilities in quantum mechanics. The root probability is based on $P(p/x)$ and $W(x)$ and there is a relative probability of $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ for a particle at x to have a momentum p . If a measurement is done even internally (or there is a hit from the stochastic potential), p may change to p_1 at x so one has a product probability when considering measurements over all space i.e. one has the new relative probability $a(p)\exp(ipx) a(p_1) \exp(i p_1x)$. Summed over p and p_1 this yields spatial density $P(x)$. If one takes a measurement, say $f(p,x)$, $f(p,x)a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is the relative probability of the value of $f(p,x)$ at x multiplied by $a(p_1)\exp(i p_1x)$ because the state of the particle may have changed during the measurement (even if it is an internal measurement). Formally, this second average may be written as: $P(x)P(p/x) f(p)$. One sums on p and integrates over all space unlike the average $\text{Sum over } p f(p)P(p/x)$ which only holds at a point.

In the $P(p/x)$ approach based on $\exp(ipx)$, a shift in position yields an extra phase shift of $p \delta(x)$. Thus:

$$\exp(ip \delta(x)) = 1 + ip \delta(x) - pp/2 \delta(x)\delta(x) + \dots \quad ((6))$$

Using $P(x+\delta(x))= W(x+\delta(x)) W(x+\delta(x))$ one has:

$$P(x+\delta(x))= 1+ \delta(x)\delta(x) [d \ln(W)/dx d \ln(W)/dx + 1/W d/dx d/x W] + 2\delta(x) d/dx \ln(W)$$

$$\text{Approx} = \exp\{ \delta(x)\delta(x) [d \ln(W)/dx d \ln(W)/dx + 1/W d/dx d/x W] + 2\delta(x) d/dx \ln(W) \} \quad ((7))$$

It should be noted that $-id \ln(W)/dx = [\text{Sum over } p p P(p/x)] / W(x)$ i.e. the average momentum at a point x . In addition, $d/dx d/dx W$ is negative. ((7)) holds for a small δx , but one may use a product of $P(x+\delta | x)$ for small steps to create a finite one. It is not clear that ((7)) is always a Gaussian i.e. that the exponent is always negative. The coefficient of $(\delta x)(\delta x)$ may be written as $1/(WW) d/dx (Wd/dxW)$. $1/(WW)$ is always positive. $\int d/dx (Wd/x W) dx$ is 0 as W dies down at the endpoints so the integrand $d/dx (W dW/dx)$ must be positive for some x and negative for others. The dominant term of the exponent of ((7)), however, should be the linear $\delta(x)$ coefficient for $\delta(x)$ small. In entropic dynamics, one has unknown constant coefficients of $(\delta x) (\delta x)$ and (δx) and can assign various values to them, even approaching infinite (1).

One may note that the coefficient of $\delta(x)\delta(x)$ is: $1/(WW) d/dx (W dW/dx)$ which is proportional to the change in the "second type of average" of momentum at each x divided by spatial density. One may also note that the coefficient of $\delta(x)$ i.e. $d/dx \ln(W)$ is the average momentum at x . This is very similar to the entropic dynamical value of $d/dx \phi$ i.e. the derivative of the drift potential which is to represent a drift velocity used in entropic dynamics. In

fact, it is later shown in (1), that ϕ is proportional to the phase of the wavefunction $W(x) = \sqrt{\text{density}(x)} \exp(i \Phi)$ where $\Phi = b \phi$. This form describes an unbound wavefunction, as a bound $W(x)$ is real, but in ((7)) the drift velocity is related to the average derivative (d/dx) of each single particle phase i.e. p from $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, the interpretation of the linear $\delta(x)$ coefficient seems to be very similar. The coefficient of the quadratic $\delta(x)\delta(x)$ is more explicit in ((7)) than in ((4)) as it is linked to average p and average p squared at x . For the ground state of a harmonic oscillator, this value is a constant, but otherwise seems to be a function of x . In ((4)) it seems constants are used in the coefficient of $\delta(x)\delta(x)$.

Considerations of Time

In (1) the argument of the exponent in ((4)) is written in terms of velocities, with $d\phi/dx$ considered to be a drift velocity. The coefficient of $\delta x(a,n)$ is $a^{-1} d\phi/dx$. In ((7)) from $P(p/x)$, the coefficient of the linear $\delta x(a,n)$ term is $2 d \ln W / dx$ which is 2 times an average momentum.

In ((4)) the coefficient of $\delta x(a,n) \delta x(b,n)$ is $an/2$ and the author considers “an” proportional to $1/(\delta t)^3$ where δt is the change in time. (In an earlier paper, the author also considered an proportional to $1/\delta t$ as a different ansatz.) In ((7)) i.e. the $P(p/x)$ approach, “an” is fixed as:

$$2(d \ln W / dx)^2 + 1/2 W d^2/dx^2 W \quad ((8))$$

This is a function of x unlike the case of entropic dynamics.

$-i d \ln(W)/dx$ is average momentum at x and $-d/dx d/dx W/W$ the average momentum squared. Thus, the coefficient of $\delta x \delta x$ is proportional to a kind of momentum squared in ((8)) and one does not have the freedom to link it to δt in different ways. If anything, momentum squared is proportional to $1/[\delta t * \delta t]$ if δx is constant at different x points and hence δt changes with x . (It may be noted that when dealing with spatial density $W(x)W(x)$, dx may be held constant around each point x . This is also done when considering the classical scenario (correspondence principle). In such a case $dt = dx/v(x)$ and δt changes with x because average momentum changes with x (as given in ((8))).

A possible issue with the time interpretation applied to ((8)) is that there are two times. First, $\langle p \rangle / m = -i d/dx \ln W$ leading to a δt_1 if δx is held fixed. The square root of $-d/dx d/dx W / W$ divided by m (mass), however, yields an rms velocity which differs from $\langle p \rangle / m$ and yields a different δt e.g. δt_2 . It is not clear which should be used, if either at all.

Subquantum Motion

In (1) it is suggested that subquantum motion occurs in a system. The $P(p/x)$ approach also allows for the idea of sub-quantum motion i.e. stochastic motion of a particle due to momentum hits from a stochastic potential that is only on average $V(x)$. In such a case, $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ is the probability based on average motion and does not specifically describe stochastic motion through time. Time in $\exp(-iEt)$ is suggested to apply to an ensemble.

Consideration of the Schrodinger Equation

The $P(p/x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ approach leads immediately to the time-independent Schrodinger equation through conservation of average energy at each x i.e.:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)]/W + V(x) = E \quad (9)$$

A more complicated approach is used in (1) to ultimately obtain the Schrodinger equation. The approach appears to be linked to a continuity equation using spatial density which is also used for derivations that do not make use of entropic dynamics e.g. (2).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we compare $P(x_1)= P(x_1 | x) P(x)$ using $P(x)=\text{Sum over } p, p_1 a(p)\exp(ipx)a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)$ and find an expression for $P(x_1 | x)$ for $x_1-x =$ an infinitesimal value. We compare this with the result from entropic dynamics (1) and find that the forms are similar i.e. both lead to a form: $\exp(-\delta(x) B + \delta(x) C d\Phi/dx)$ where $d\Phi/dx$ is related to a drift velocity. For the approach of $P(p/x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)/W$, B is a function of x proportional to $d \ln(W)/dx d \ln(W)/dx + 1/W d/dx d/dx W$ i.e. the average momentum at a point squared - the average momentum squared at a point whereas entropic dynamics treats B for an infinitesimal δx as a constant and suggests it may be related to $1/(\delta t)^3$. The drift term $C d\Phi/dx$ is very similar to the term $2 d \ln(W)/dx$ in the $P(p/x)$ approach.

Furthermore, the entropic dynamical approach maximizes entropy in order to obtain $P(x_1 | x)$ whereas we argue that $\exp(ipx)$ (part of $P(p/x)$) already displays entropic maximization because it treats all x points equivalently in the sense that its modulus is 1 everywhere. $\exp(ipx)$ is a function of p and x because it is used to calculate average kinetic energy at a point and this must vary according to: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$.

In both the $P(p/x)$ approach and entropic dynamics, it is suggested there may be sub-quantum motion. $P(p/x)$, we argue, gives a momentum probability distribution at each x , but actual motion is stochastic. The $P(p/x)$ approach differs from entropic dynamics in that it describes information about p at each x point and is based on $W(x)$ instead of considering changes based on $W(x)W(x)$.

References

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